

Diffusion of Polymers through Periodic Networks of Lipid-Based Nanochannels

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Abstract

We present an experimental investigation of the diffusion of unfolded polymers in the triply-periodic water-channel network of inverse bicontinuous cubic phases. Depending on the chain size, our results indicate the presence of two different dynamical regimes corresponding to Zimm and Rouse diffusion. We support our findings by scaling arguments based on a combination of blob and effective-medium theories and suggest the presence of a third regime where dynamics is driven by reptation. Our experimental results also show an increasing behavior of the partition coefficient as a function of the polymer molecular weight, indicative of a reduction in the conformational degrees of freedom induced by the confinement.

Introduction

Inverse bicontinuous cubic phases (IBCPs) are an intriguing class of lipid-based membranes characterized by a three-dimensional (3D) periodic structure on the nanometer scale.^{1,2} Within these objects, the lipid bilayer separates two interpenetrating networks of noncommunicating water channels and arranges them according to specific geometrical symmetries, the most common being the diamond, primitive, and gyroid lattices. IBCPs have been observed *in vivo* in stressed or infected cells.³⁻⁵ Moreover, the periodic and geometrical features of IBCPs can be closely controlled *in vitro*,⁶⁻¹³ thus making them ideal biomimetic systems for several nanotechnological applications, including food technology, membrane protein crystallization, ion pumps, and drug delivery.¹⁴⁻¹⁸

The potential use of IBCPs in such disparate areas has recently boosted a large number of studies characterizing their transport properties.^{9,16,19-27} However, the vast majority of these works have focused on the diffusion of small particles, whereas only a few of them have dealt with structured or unfolded macromolecules. In spite of the great interest in the transport properties of IBCPs, till now, a systematic analysis relating the size of an unfolded polymer to its diffusing properties within cubic phases is still lacking.

Apart from its importance in the practical use of IBCPs in nanotechnological applications, an investigation in this direction is also of general interest from the polymer physics perspective. Indeed, experimental works on polymer dynamics in dilute solutions have used confining objects such as uniform tubes, adsorbing surfaces, or random porous media,²⁸⁻³⁵ but, to our knowledge, there exists no study on the diffusion of a chain through ordered 3D structures. In this regard, IBCPs offer a unique possibility to fill this gap.

In the present work, we report an experimental study addressing the dynamics of unfolded polymers diffusing within cubic phases and rationalize our findings by means of scaling arguments. Depending on the relative magnitude between the polymer size and the length scales characterizing the microscopic features of the IBCP, our data identify two different dynamic regimes in the system. These results are in line with predictions based on de

Gennes' blob arguments,³⁶ which in turn suggest the presence of a third regime not observed in experiments, most likely due to practical limitations.

Materials and experimental methods

Materials

Polyethylene glycols (PEGs) of different molecular weights were purchased from Polymer Source Inc. All molecular weights considered were highly monodispersed, with a polydispersity index in the range 1.05 – 1.08. Dimodan was received as a gift from Danisco (Denmark). Dimodan is the commercial name of monolinolein, the lipid used for making the cubic phases as explained below. The commercial-grade form of such monolinolein contains more than 98 wt % monoglyceride.

Functionalization of PEGs

PEGs were functionalized using a reported protocol.³⁷ Fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) was used as the functionalizing agent. PEGs were reacted with a large excess of FITC. For example, 80 mg of 6.7k PEG and 20 mg of FITC were dissolved in dimethylformamide (DMF). Then, the solution was kept at 90 °C overnight. After removing DMF using a rotary evaporator, the mixture was dispersed in Milli-Q water. To separate the unreacted solutes (unreacted FITC), the solution was filtered using 0.45 cellulose membranes. The filtrate was dialyzed against Milli-Q water for 3 days. The final product was freeze-dried for 4 days. ¹H NMR showed that PEGs were successfully functionalized with FITC.

Polymer Solutions

Milli-Q grade water was used as solvent for making PEG solutions. All of the polymers used in the experiments were prepared below the overlapping concentration (C^*), that is,

they meet the dilute regime condition. To estimate the overlap concentration, we used the following equation

$$C^* = \frac{M}{N_A \frac{4}{3}\pi R_g^3} \quad (1)$$

where M and N_A are the molecular weight of the polymer and the Avogadro number, respectively. R_g is calculated by the empirical formula³⁸

$$R_g \simeq 0.0145M^{0.571} \text{ nm} \quad (2)$$

Table 2 reports the initial concentration C_i of the polymer solutions used in each experiment and the values of C^* .

Table 1: Recapitulation of the Results from the Release and Diffusion Experiments Together with the Properties of the System Considered. The number of monomers was computed by considering the weight of each repeating unit equal to 48 Da. R_g and R_w were computed using eqs 2 and 5.

molecular weight (Da)	number of monomers	R_g (nm)	R_g/R_w	$D_m \times 10^7$ (cm ² /s)	k
2.4k	50	1.23	0.71	3.4 ± 0.1	
3.3k	69	1.48	0.88	3.3 ± 0.2	3.2 ± 0.1
5k	104	1.88	1.05	2.0 ± 0.1	5.7 ± 0.2
6.7k	140	2.22	1.25	2.3 ± 0.1	4.9 ± 0.3
11k	229	2.94	1.63	1.2 ± 0.1	10.3 ± 0.1
20k	417	4.14	2.35	0.64 ± 0.01	6.0 ± 0.6
32k	667	5.42	2.94	0.38 ± 0.03	14.6 ± 0.5

Description of the Release and Diffusion Experiments

The cubic phase used here maintains its structure even under excess-water conditions.⁹ This offers the possibility to probe the diffusion properties of the IBCP by putting it in contact with water-containing chambers. We considered two experimental approaches from the literature, namely, the Release^{19,20,26} and Diffusion^{9,20} setups.

In the release setup, the cubic phase is formed by mixing the monolinolein with a dilute

Table 2: Initial Concentration Used in the Release and Diffusion Experiments and the Overlapping Concentration for Each PEG. The last column lists the overlapping concentration for each PEG, calculated using eq 1.

M (g/mol)	C_i in release (mg/mL)	C_i in diffusion (mg/mL)	C^* (mg/mL)
2.4k	0.05		506
3.3k	0.2	0.2	403
5k	0.2	0.2	300
6.7k	0.2	0.2	243
11k	0.15	0.1	171
20k	0.6	0.1	112
32k	0.1	0.85	80

solution of monodispersed PEG in water, so that the polymers are initially distributed within its water channels. The relative amount of water and monolinolein was chosen in order for the system to lie at the border with excess-water conditions, that is, adding more water does not result in further structural changes in the mesophase. The IBCP is then inserted into a cylindrical tube and put in contact with a receiving chamber filled with Milli-Q water (see inset in the central panel of Figure 1). Driven by the difference in the chemical potential between the two phases, IBCP and water, the polymers are released from the former to the latter. By periodically replacing the content of the receiving chamber with Milli-Q water, one can mimic perfect sink conditions. Moreover, by checking the concentration of the polymers in the removed solution, the release kinetics can be monitored in time.

In the diffusion setup, the IBCP is initially free of polymers. When inserted into the tube, it is placed between a delivering chamber containing the PEG solution and a receiving one filled with Milli-Q water (see inset in the right panel of Figure 1). In this way, a chain can diffuse into the receiving chamber only by passing through the cubic phase. Again, perfect sink conditions are mimicked by periodically reloading the receiving chamber with Milli-Q water, and the kinetics of the process is monitored by measuring the amount of diffused macromolecules.

Preparation of the Cubic Phases for Release and Diffusion Experiments

In the case of release experiments, the polymer solution and Dimodan were mixed in Pyrex tubes and homogenized afterward by several cycles of heating and vortex mixing. At the final stage, the entire cubic phase, made from the lipid and the polymer solution, was centrifuged for 30 min at 4000 rpm. The temperature under centrifugation stage was set to 37 °C. After the centrifugation step, the sample was placed in an oven at 37 °C for 6 days to reach the thermodynamic equilibrium.

For diffusion experiments, Milli-Q-grade water and Dimodan were mixed in Pyrex tubes and homogenized afterward by several cycles of heating and vortex mixing. The cubic phase was let to equilibrate for 3 days at 37 °C; then, it was transferred using a spatula from the Pyrex tube to a long tube, following ref.⁹ The cubic phase was placed in the middle of the long tube with Teflon pistons, finally obtaining a disk of thickness of 6 ± 0.1 mm. The tube was then put in the refrigerator overnight to crystallize the cubic phase. In the following step, the pistons were smoothly removed to avoid any damage on the surface of the cubic phase. Both chambers, that is, the right and left sides of the cubic phase, were filled with fresh Milli-Q water. Then, the lipid-based cubic phase was kept for 7 days in the oven at 37 °C for equilibration in the presence of excess water. Once the equilibration process was over, both chambers were emptied; one of them (called the delivering chamber) was filled with a fresh polymer solution, whereas the other (receiving chamber) was refilled with fresh Milli-Q water.

Characterization of the Cubic Phases

Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) measurements were used to identify the symmetry of the IBCP and to determine the lattice parameters of the liquid crystalline structures. SAXS diffractograms were acquired using a Bruker microfocused X-ray source of wavelength,

Figure 1: Left panel: Four-fold repeating structure of one network of water channels within the double-diamond symmetry and the representative diffusing polymer. Central panel: Examples of release profiles together with best fits using eq 6. Inset: Sketch of the release setup. Right panel: Examples of diffusion profiles with the corresponding fitting lines using eq 7. Inset: Schematics of the diffusion setup. Throughout this work, when not shown, error bars are smaller than the size of the symbols.

Figure 2: Release profiles with the corresponding fits for PEGs with molecular weights 2.4, 5, 11, and 32 kDa.

$\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$ operating at 50 kV and 1 mA. The diffracted X-ray signal was collected in a gas-filled two-dimensional detector. The scattering vector embedded image, with 2θ being the scattering angle, was calibrated using silver behenate. The q -range was assessed to be in the range $0.004 - 0.5 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. Data were collected and azimuthally averaged using the Saxes GUI software to yield the one-dimensional intensity (1D) versus the scattering vector q . The samples were loaded in the Linkam hot stage between two thin mica sheets and sealed using an O-ring with a sample thickness of approximately 1 mm. Measurements were taken at $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The samples were equilibrated for 30 min before measurements, whereas the scattered intensity was collected over 0.5 h. Figure S1A illustrates the SAXS results for the cubic phases used in the release experiments for the PEG-11k case before and after the experiment. It is important to note that for each release experiment, the hydration of the cubic phase, in equilibrium with excess water or polymer solution, was always in the range 33 – 36%. Therefore, the presence of polymers within the water channels does not perturb strongly the structure of the IBCP. Similar to the release experiment, SAXS measurements were used to identify the symmetry of the IBCPs. The SAXS spectra depicted in Figure S1B were acquired from the cubic phase used in a typical diffusion experiment. The small shift to the left in the spectra after the diffusion experiment is attributed to a slight dehydration of the cubic phase.

From the information acquired from the SAXS measurements, the lattice parameter (a) can be computed as

$$a = \frac{2\pi}{q^*} \sqrt{2} \quad (3)$$

where q^* corresponds to the first peak in the SAXS spectra.

Using the geometrical features of the cubic phases, the lipid length (l_{lip}) within the bilayer can be obtained by solving the following equation³⁹

$$\varphi_{lip} = 2A_0 \frac{l_{lip}}{a} + \frac{4}{3} \pi \chi \left(\frac{l_{lip}}{a} \right)^3 \quad (4)$$

where φ_{lip} is the lipid volume fraction, A_0 is the minimal surface in a unit cell to (unit cell volume)^{2/3}, and χ is the Euler–Poincaré characteristic. For the Pn3m case, we have $A_0 = 1.919$ and $\chi = -2$, thus obtaining $l_{lip} = 1.6$ nm. Once l_{lip} is known, the radius of the water channel is estimated using the following equation³⁹

$$R_w = 0.391a - l_{lip} = 1.8 \text{ nm} \quad (5)$$

Ultraviolet–Visible (UV–vis) Spectroscopy

UV–vis method was used to determine the wavelength at which the functionalized polymer solutions are excited, which was determined to be 490 nm. An UV–vis spectrometer Varian Cary 300, version 10.00 was used. The measurements were conducted with a quartz cuvette at room temperature.

Fluorescence Measurements

The concentrations of the diffusion and release samples were quantified using fluorimetry measurements, using a Jobin–Yvon Horiba Fluoromax 4 spectrofluorometer. The measurements were performed with a quartz cuvette and an excitation wavelength of 490 nm (acquired from the UV–vis absorption spectrum). The emission wavelength was detected at 513 nm for the samples.

Results and discussion

In our experiments, we considered cubic phases based on a mixture of monolinolein and water.^{9,20} As the direct inspection using small–angle X–ray spectroscopy shows, this choice results in an IBCP with a double–diamond symmetry, described by the Pn3m space group⁹ (see Figure S1). As a model polymer chain, we used polyethylene glycol, whose hydrophilicity ensures that diffusion takes place within the water channels. To be able to detect the

PEG molecules, we functionalized them with the fluorescently active dye FITC. Further experimental details can be found in Materials and Experimental Methods. The left panel of Figure 1 illustrates schematically a repeating unit of a Pn3m cubic phase. For simplicity, only one four-folded network of water channels is drawn (blue) together with one surface of the lipid bilayer (yellow). A representative polymer entering the unit at a given instant (red) diffuses out of it at a later time τ (brown).

Release Experiments

To study the dynamic properties of the diffusing polymers, we performed a series of release experiments, each involving a monodispersed solution of PEG with a given molecular weight. The range of accessible values of polymer sizes was limited because of experimental issues. Indeed, on one hand, very small polymers would have sizes comparable to that of the dye, so that the latter would dominate the diffusion dynamics. On the other hand, attaining an efficient functionalization and an adequate monodispersity becomes unfeasible for large molecular weights. We found that for our system, reliable results could be obtained when considering polymer weights between 3.3 and 32 kDa. In the central panel of Figure 1, we plot the percentage of released chains as a function of time for three representative polymer sizes, whereas the other release kinetics are reported in Figure 2 (for all release profiles at a glance, see Figure S2). As one may expect, larger polymers are released more slowly, and the release curves are consequently delayed. Because of the large-scale separation between the microscopic features of the IBCP (order of nanometers) and its overall size (order of millimeters), the cubic phase can be treated as a homogeneous medium where the polymer moves with an effective diffusion constant, which is lower than the same quantity in pure water. Within this effective medium approximation, the release kinetics can be modeled as a simple 1D diffusive process taking place along the axis of the cylindrical tube, where the receiving chamber can be included as an adsorbing boundary condition at the IBCP-chamber interface⁴⁰ while a reflective wall is assumed to be present on the other side of the

cubic phase. The dependence of the total fraction of the released molecules Q on time can then be computed using standard methods⁴¹ and reads

$$Q(t) = 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2} e^{-(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 D_m t / 4h^2} \quad (6)$$

where $h \simeq 0.6$ cm is the size of the cubic phase. By tuning the value of D_m , we performed a fit of the release profiles, considering the first 20 terms of eq 6 and obtaining the full curves reported in the central panel of Figure 1 and in Figure 2.

Figure 3: Effective diffusion coefficient retrieved from the release experiments vs the polymer molecular weight. The lines correspond to the expected slopes from the Zimm (continuous green line) and Rouse models (dashed blue line).

In Figure 3, we plot in log-log scale the optimizing value of D_m as a function of the molecular weight M of the polymer (see Table 1 for the numerical values). The data outline

the presence of two regimes characterized by a power-law behavior with different exponents, with a faster decay in the region corresponding to larger polymers. The two regimes are well-described by the Zimm and Rouse dynamics, characterized by scaling exponents equal to $-3/5$ and -1 , respectively.

From a physical viewpoint, these results indicate that confinement affects the dynamical properties of short and long polymers in distinct ways. Qualitatively, for small chains, the center of mass is prevented to access the volume occupied by the lipid bilayer, whereas both their conformation and local dynamics are unaffected by the confinement. Consequently, the diffusion within the mesophase is slower than its counterpart in free water only because of the labyrinthine path provided by the network of water channels, so that the scaling dependence of D_m on M is still described by the well-known Zimm dynamics.³⁶ For longer polymers, the confinement also reduces the conformational degrees of freedom, and the chain diffuses as a collection of hydrodynamically uncoupled blobs characterized by the Rouse dynamics.⁴²

Diffusion Experiments

The conclusions reached in the previous section are further supported by independent experiments performed with the diffusion setup. In the right panel of Figure 1, we report illustrative diffusion profiles corresponding to three different PEG sizes (see Figure S3 for the full set of diffusion kinetics). Similar to the release case, larger polymers diffuse more slowly. Moreover, comparing the central and right panels of Figure 1, one can notice that for any molecular weight, the diffusion kinetics is slower than its release counterpart. This is partly due to the larger distance travelled by a typical chain in a diffusion experiment (delivering chamber plus IBCP) with respect to the release case (only IBCP). Nevertheless, a key role is expected to be played by the free-energy barrier ΔF that a polymer has to overcome to enter the IBCP from the delivering chamber because of the decrease in its translational and conformational entropies. This feature can be captured by the partition coefficient $k \equiv \exp(\Delta F/k_B T)$, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T is the tempera-

ture, with $k > 1$ being the distinctive trait of a barrier.⁴³ It can be shown that the diffusion kinetics depends linearly on time as

$$Q(t) = \frac{D_m t}{k L h} \quad (7)$$

where $L \simeq 3$ cm is the size of the delivering chamber.⁴³ As we show in the right panel of Figure 1, the data are indeed nicely fitted into a straight line (see also Figure S3). Combining the optimizing values of the slope (reported in the inset of Figure 4) and the fit for D_m obtained from the release experiments, we can estimate the values of k , which are plotted in Figure 4 as a function of M (see also Table 1). In all cases, we get $k > 1$, which is the fingerprint of an entropic barrier. Besides, the value of the partition coefficient generally increases with the molecular weight, which is a direct consequence of the reduction in the conformational space, in line with the conclusions reached in the previous section.

Scaling Model of Polymer Diffusion through IBCPs

The findings reported above strongly point toward the presence of distinct conformational and dynamical regimes and can be rationalized by scaling arguments. To this aim, we note that the diffusion behavior of the chain depends on the relative magnitude between its radius of gyration in free water R_g and the characteristic lengths of the network of water channels, epitomized by the lattice parameter a and the average channel radius R_w (see the left panel of Figure 1). The quantity $a = 8.4$ nm is directly extracted from the SAXS spectra (shown in Figure S1) using eq 3, whereas $R_w = 1.8$ nm can be estimated using geometrical arguments (see eq 5).

If $R_g \lesssim R_w$, the presence of the channels does not alter the conformational properties of the polymer, as we sketch in the bottom-left corner of Figure 3. Also hydrodynamic interactions (HI) among monomers are unaffected because the screening due to confinement becomes effective only at distances larger than R_w .⁴² In this case, the only role played by

Figure 4: Partition coefficient obtained from the combination of release and diffusion experiments vs the polymer molecular weight. Inset: Slopes of linear fits of the diffusion profiles vs the polymer molecular weight.

the cubic phase is to restrict the volume available at the center of mass of the polymer to a fraction ϕ of the total extension of the system. ϕ can be identified with half of the amount of water used to form the IBCP, that is, $\phi \simeq 0.17$. According to the effective-medium theory,⁴⁴ the large-scale diffusivity in the porous medium is then given by $D_m \simeq f(\phi)D_0$, where $f(\phi)$ depends on the geometrical distribution of the obstacles and $D_0 \approx k_B T / \eta R_g$ is the self-diffusion coefficient of the chain in pure water, as predicted by the Zimm model, η being the viscosity of water.⁴⁵ Therefore, in this regime, $D_m \propto R_g^{-1} \propto M^{-\nu}$, where $\nu \simeq 3/5$ is the Flory exponent. As we show in Figure 3, this scaling prediction nicely captures the trend of the experimental data in the low-molecular-weight regime (continuous green line).

If $R_g \gtrsim R_w$, the polymer adopts an elongated shape typical of 1D confinement and can be represented as a chain of blobs of size R_w .⁴⁶ Within each blob, the polymer retains the same conformations as in free water. As a consequence, $R_w \approx bg^\nu$, where b is the size of a segment and g is the number of monomers in a blob. If N is the number of segments composing the polymer, the total number of blobs n_b is thus given by $n_b \equiv N/g \approx (R_g/R_w)^{1/\nu}$, and the contour length l_b of the blob chain is $l_b \approx n_b R_w$. The relative magnitude of l_b with respect to the lattice parameter a outlines two qualitatively different behaviors of the system. When $l_b \lesssim a \Rightarrow R_g \lesssim R_w (a/R_w)^\nu$, the polymer can be entirely embedded in a single channel, that is, a typical conformation does not explore the network structure. This situation can be ascribed to the simple case of a long chain in a cylindrical tube, whose dynamical properties were addressed by Brochard and de Gennes.⁴² Although originally derived from the Kirkwood theory, their results can also be obtained by simple blob arguments. Indeed, in the present context, the diffusion coefficient of a blob D_b can be estimated as $D_b \approx f(\phi)k_B T / \eta R_w$. Because of the screening of HI for distances larger than R_w , different blobs are expected not to be hydrodynamically coupled. As a result, the blob chain behaves as a Rouse polymer,⁴⁵ and its diffusion coefficient is $D_m \approx D_b/n_b \approx f(\phi)k_B T / (\eta R_w) (R_g/R_w)^{-1/\nu} \propto M^{-1}$. The Rouse scaling behavior is reported in Figure 3 as a dashed blue line and shows a good agreement with the points corresponding to large molecular weights. Finally, if $l_b \gtrsim a \Rightarrow R_g \gtrsim R_w (a/R_w)^\nu$, a

typical chain conformation is spread over several water channels, and the expected dynamical behavior is that predicted by the reptation theory.³⁶ In the present case, the polymer can be coarse-grained at the level of lattice units and represented as a self-avoiding walk with step a . The number of segments n_a is equal, up to a prefactor, to l_b/a , and the size of the chain is $R \approx an_a^\nu$. The reptating polymer is constrained to slide along its contour length according to the Rouse dynamics described above, characterized by the diffusion coefficient D_b/n_b . Following de Gennes³⁶ and neglecting effects due to the fluctuations in the contour length,⁴⁵ one can estimate the reptation time τ_{rep} by considering either the sliding diffusion $\tau_{rep} \approx l_b^2/(D_b/n_b)$ or the Brownian motion of the center of mass $\tau_{rep} \approx R^2/D_m$. This enables us to compute D_m in the present case as $D_m \approx (R/l_b)^2 D_b/n_b \approx f(\phi)k_B T/(\eta R_w)(R_g/R_w)^{2-3/\nu}(R_w/a)^{2\nu-2}$. We note that R_w/a depends only on ϕ (see eqs 8 and 9 in Materials and Experimental Methods). Therefore, the previous formula can be written as $D_m \approx g(\phi)k_B T/(\eta R_w)(R_g/R_w)^{2-3/\nu}$, where $g(\phi)$ is suitably defined. Unfortunately, the range of experimentally accessible polymer weights (see above) does not include values of M large enough to experimentally access this regime, where $D_m \propto M^{2\nu-3} \simeq M^{-1.8}$. According to our analysis, the quantity $D_m R_w$ depends on R_g and R_w only by their ratio

$$\begin{cases} f(\phi) \frac{k_B T}{\eta} \left(\frac{R_g}{R_w}\right)^{-1} & \frac{R_g}{R_w} \lesssim 1 \\ f(\phi) \frac{k_B T}{\eta} \left(\frac{R_g}{R_w}\right)^{-1/\nu} & 1 \lesssim \frac{R_g}{R_w} \lesssim \left(\frac{a}{R_w}\right)^\nu \\ g(\phi) \frac{k_B T}{\eta} \left(\frac{R_g}{R_w}\right)^{2-3/\nu} & \frac{R_g}{R_w} \gtrsim \left(\frac{a}{R_w}\right)^\nu \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

In Figure 5, we plot the experimental data rescaled according to the prescription above (red circles). The values of R_g were estimated according to an empirical formula based on dynamic light scattering experiments (see eq 2 in Materials and Experimental Methods). A customary approach to providing a single fit consists of considering a double-power law of the form^{47,48}

$$D_m R_w \approx \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{R_g}{R_w}\right)^{-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{R_g}{R_w}\right)^{1/\alpha}\right]^{\alpha(-\frac{1}{\nu}+1)} \quad (9)$$

Figure 5: Rescaled diffusion coefficient $D_m R_w$ as a function of the ratio R_g/R_w for the same set of data considered in Figure 3 in log–log (main plot) and lin–lin (inset) scales.

The previous formula enables a smooth transition from the Zimm to the Rouse regime (reported as dashed lines), with c indicating the turning point and α quantifying the extent of the transition region. The continuous line reported in Figure 5 corresponds to $c \simeq 1.2$ and $\alpha \simeq 0.1$ and shows that the change in slope occurs close to $R_g/R_w = 1$, in agreement with the scaling theory. Nevertheless, we stress that the latter does not provide the exact numerical coefficients, so that the transition point could have been located farther from 1 without affecting the validity of the theory. Another important point is that eq 8 does not consider the reptation regime; thus, it cannot be extrapolated to larger values of R_g/R_w . Interestingly, in eq 8, the numerical coefficients depend only on ϕ . Therefore, the results corresponding to Pn3m cubic phases with different geometrical features are expected to follow the master curve reported in Figure 5, as long as the value of ϕ is maintained.

The blob picture also enables a simple description of the partition coefficient. In the Zimm regime, the confinement of the center of mass plays a leading role in determining the confinement free energy. Consequently, one has $k \simeq 1/\Phi \simeq 3$, where $\Phi = 2\phi$ is the *total* available volume fraction within the two sets of water channels. Conversely, in the Rouse and reptation regimes, also the lower number of available conformations has to be taken into account. The corresponding decrease in the entropy can be estimated as $\Delta S \approx k_B n_b \approx M$,³⁶ thus giving $k \simeq \exp(\gamma M)/\Phi$, where γ is a suitable constant. Unfortunately, the values of the partition coefficient extracted from the experiments are too noisy to conclusively compare them with theory.

Conclusions

Here, we have performed for the first time a systematic study on the diffusion properties of unstructured polymers in IBCPs, focusing on their effective diffusion coefficient D_m and the partition coefficient k . The experimental data point toward the presence of distinct regimes associated with different relative magnitudes of the chains with respect to the confining media. Combining considerations from effective-medium theories and scaling arguments, we elucidated how the interplay between such length scales determines the transport properties of unfolded macromolecules within cubic phases, thus providing a basis to devise optimized systems for their practical applications. An interesting question is related to how these features are affected by the symmetry and the geometry of the IBCP,⁴⁹ which will be addressed in a future study. From a polymer physics perspective, cubic phases provide a novel material environment for chain diffusion within well-ordered 3D media. Our results appoint them as suggestive model systems, where as many as three different regimes are present, encompassing the main single-molecule theories for the undriven motion of unfolded polymers.

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